

Hollow Ball Core (HBC) Technology for Novel Sandwich Structured Composites

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- **Introduction and motivation**
- **Hollow Ball Core(HBC) Manufacturing Approach for Panel Tests**
- **Characterization of HBC Panels**
- **Key Advantages and Applications**
- **Future Works & Acknowledgements**

01

Introduction and Research Motivation

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Corrugated Core

Truss Core

3D Printed Core

- **Limitation: Sandwich for Complex Structures**
 - Complex curvatures
 - Cylinders and enclosed molds

01 Introduction and Research Motivation

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- Key Advantages

- HBC can accommodate the **complex geometry** sandwich structures only through ball packing optimization
- 100% recyclable materials (thermoplastics) are used

- Potential Applications

- Replacing closed mold processes (e.g., UAM parts)
- Enclosed molds

02 Hollow Ball Core material properties

Cutaway view of HBC unit cell

Thermoplastic ball

02 Hollow Ball Core material properties

Thermoplastic ball

02 DSC – crystallization kinetics for heating/cooling rate control

02 Dynamic Mechanical Analysis

- DSC & DMA results validation
- Identify Interdiffusion temperature
- Onset point,
 - rapid drop of storage modulus E'
- $166^{\circ}\text{C} = 330^{\circ}\text{F}$
 - Initial process temperature

- Glass transition temperature, but below melting temperature

03 Hollow Ball Core(HBC) Manufacturing Process

- **Experimental Procedure and Processing Flow**
 - Material property
 - Heating
 - Pressing and bonding
 - Cooling
 - Bonding check
 - Structure testing

03 HBC Manufacturing Process

Single cell without mold

The reduced height after compaction is approximately 60% of ball diameter

03 HBC Manufacturing Process

- Thermoplastic (Polypropylene – PP) hollow spheres are heat-pressed
- Dwell time 10 min at 340 °F

Temperature probe location k-type

03 Hollow Ball Core(HBC) Manufacturing Process

- Thermoplastic (Polypropylene – PP) hollow spheres are heat-pressed
- Cell bonding temperature 350 °F
- Ramping up temperature
- Press is already completed at this point

Cell fail to weld with lower temperature

03 Hollow Ball Core(HBC) Manufacturing Process

- Thermoplastic (Polypropylene – PP) hollow spheres are cooled
- Crystallization temperature 266°F
- Cooling methods
 - Water cooled
 - Air cooled
- Press is already completed at this point

04 HBC Manufacturing Process

Cooling rate and smooth surface process

<https://blogs.solidworks.com/tech/2018/09/your-part-is-shrinking.html>

04 Characterization of HBC Panel

- Flexural Test – water vs air cooled
- Equivalent weight

- Air cooled panel showed ductility
 - Strong bond, uniform quality
 - Force distributed well thru the joints

04 Characterization of HBC Panel

- Flexural Test – HBC vs Solid
– Equivalent weight

- Fracture does not occur at the ball all interfaces
– Strong bond, uniform quality

04 Characterization of HBC Panel

- Thermoplastic (Polypropylene – PP) hollow spheres

Light Reflections from photography

- Thermally joined line is invisible
- Homogeneously welded

05 Conclusive Remarks

- Pressing was feasible near the thermoplastic's T_g
- Cell fusion occurred at higher T_g in DSC vs. DMA
- Slow cooling enhanced crystallization and bonding
- Flat mold fabrication was simple and effective
- Potential shown for use with complex molds

05 Future Work

- **Further characterization**
 - HBC manufacture effect on tensile strength
 - HBC impact strength
 - Crystallization kinetics of ball polymers
- **Process optimization**
 - Thermo-mechanical property modeling via ANSYS
 - Improved temperature and pressure monitoring and control

05 Acknowledgements

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Q&A

FICAM

Supplementary

02 Hollow Ball Core(HBC) Manufacturing Process

- Thermoplastic (Polypropylene – PP) hollow spheres are heat-pressed

Blow-molded hollow spheres

Heat Press

02 HBC Manufacturing Process

- Height reduction after packing

$$\frac{1}{2} \times \frac{4}{3} \pi \left(\frac{D}{2}\right)^3 = \left(\frac{D}{2} \times \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} D\right) \times H$$

$$H = \frac{\pi}{3\sqrt{3}} D$$

$$H = 0.605D$$

The reduced height after compaction is approximately 60% of ball diameter

03 Characterization of HBC Panel

Solid Panel
Same mass of material
Same area

Sample Panel
HBC geometry

Cut to same sample shape
Allows for comparative testing